

VELOCITY OF TRANSFORMATION OF 1 : 3 : 5-TRIKETONES
 INTO 2 : 6-DISUBSTITUTED γ -PYRONES. PART I. VELO-
 CITY OF TRANSFORMATION OF ACETONE DIOXALIC
 ESTER INTO CHELIDONIC ESTER.

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In order to investigate the structure of 1 : 3 : 5-triketones by physical method acetone dioxalic ester is chosen as the standard substance of comparison as its constitution is definitely known. Velocity constants of the change of this ester into chelidonic ester are given and the mechanism of the change explained.

Deshpande, Dingankar and Kopil (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **11**, 595) described the synthesis of dipropionylacetone and di-*n*-butyrylacetone. The reactions of the products led the authors to assign the structure (I, R = C₂H₅ or C₃H₇) to these compounds.

By analogy diacetylacetone should be (I, R = CH₃). The simple structure (I, R = CH₃) is, however, opposed to Collie's structure for diacetylacetone (II), based on the chemical relations of this compound to dimethylpyrone which he represents by the oxide structure formed by the loss of a molecule of water (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1904, **85**, 971).

Deshpande, Bedekar and Kaushal (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, **12**, 465) have given additional evidence in support of the open-chain structure (I, R = CH₃) for diacetylacetone and its homologues. They have shown that γ -pyrone and 2 : 6-substituted γ -pyrones have probably simple ring structure (III) rather than the bridge ring structure assumed by Collie.

(III)

(V)

In the present paper an attempt has been made to throw more light on the structure of these substances by physicochemical investigations.

The plan adopted was to make a comparison between diacetylacetone or its higher homologues and an open-chain 1:3:5-triketone, *e.g.* acetone dioxalic ester (IV), synthesised by Claisen from acetone and oxalic ester in two stages.

It is well known that acetone dioxalic ester under dehydrating conditions such as keeping in vacuum, loses a molecule of water and changes into the ring compound, chelidonic ester (V). The substance (acetone dioxalic ester) exists in monoenol and dienol forms, the dehydration taking place from the dienol form.

It has been found that for this reaction dehydrating conditions are not necessary. Acetone dioxalic ester dissolves in any non-dehydrating medium such as acetone or dilute alcohol and changes into chelidonic ester in the presence of a trace of a catalyst. It is further found that this relation is quantitative and is accompanied by no side-reactions and is one of the few reactions which are strictly unimolecular.

EXPERIMENTAL.

Acetone dioxalic ester was crystallised from glacial acetic acid and dried at low temperature, *m.p.* 100-101°. The rate of transformation was investigated by physical and chemical methods.

The known weight of acetone dioxalic ester was dissolved in a known volume of the solvent containing a known concentration of the catalyst and the reaction was carried in a thermostat at a fixed temperature. At definite intervals, a known volume of the solution was pipetted and three times the volume of water added to it. Under these conditions the chelidonic ester is completely soluble, while acetone dioxalic ester being almost insoluble, is completely precipitated. The slight correction for the solubility of the ester was introduced by determining its solubility in the mixed solvent used at the time of precipitation. From the corrected weight of the unchanged ester the rate of the chemical change was determined.

In the chemical method unchanged acetone-dioxalic ester was determined from time to time by precipitating it as insoluble copper salt with copper acetate solution. The copper salt of acetone dioxalic ester is quantitatively precipitated if to a dilute methyl or ethyl alcoholic solution of the compound aqueous copper acetate is added and under these conditions chelidonic ester remains in solution.

TABLE I.

Solvent—Acetone; Catalyst—0.015*N*-HCl. Temperature—22°. Weight of acetone dioxalic ester—4.0152 g. Volume of solution—50 c.c. Volume of the solution withdrawn each time—3 c.c. Water added—12 c.c. Solubility correction 0.0192 g in 15 c.c. of mixed solution.

Time (t).	Wt. of unchanged triketone.	Unchanged wt. (corrected).	$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{(a-x)}$.
0 min.	0.2130 g.	0.2322 (a)	—
29	0.1928	0.2120 (a-x)	0.00134
59	0.1710	0.1902	0.00134
108	0.1476	0.1668	0.00134
149	0.1282	0.1474	0.00133
211	0.1018	0.1210	0.00134
269	0.0824	0.1016	0.00133
361	0.0574	0.0766	0.00133

TABLE II.

Solvent—Acetone. Catalyst—0.0432*N*-HCl. Temperature—52°. Weight of the ester—2.7690 g. Solubility of the ester in 15 c.c. of the mixed solvent at 52°—0.0233. Other factors same as in Table I.

Time (t).	Unchanged ester.	Unchanged ester (corrected).	$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.
0 min.	0.1428	0.1661 (a)	—
10	0.1146	0.1379 (a-x)	0.0081
29	0.0738	0.0971	0.0080
45	0.0466	0.0699	0.0083
51	0.0278	0.0511	0.0084
80	0.0090	0.0323	0.0088
97	0.0010	0.0243	0.0086

TABLE III.

Chemical method.

Reaction was very rapid at 54°. Solvent—50% aqueous methyl alcohol. Strength of HCl—0.0402 *N*. Temperature—54°. Weight of ester—0.1634g. Volume of the solution—96 c.c. Volume of the solution precipitated as copper salt each time—20 c.c.

Time (t).	Wt. of Cu salt.	$k_1 = \frac{1}{t} \log \frac{a}{a-x}$.
0 min.	0.0393	—
5	0.0270	0.0325
23	0.0070	0.0325

These results clearly show the unimolecular nature of the transformation of acetone dioxalic ester into chelidonic ester.

DISCUSSION.

Acetone dioxalic ester exists as an equilibrium mixture in solution of its keto-enolic forms since it is the enolic form which undergoes dehydration into chelidonic ester :

If C_1 and C_2 are their respective concentrations at equilibrium then

$$\frac{C_2}{C_1} = \text{constant } (m) \quad \dots \text{ (i)}$$

Again the enolic form changes into chelidonic ester which is one-sided reaction as the change goes to completion

If $a-x$ is the concentration of enol form at any time t , initial concentration being a , then,

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k(a-x) \quad \dots \text{ (ii)}$$

Thus we have to consider both the reactions simultaneously.

Let a be the initial concentration of keto form and b , be the concentration of enol form at any time t and x be the change in concentration of the

and form in the same time t , then the concentration of unchanged keto form at the same time is $a - b - x$.

But by equation (i)
$$\frac{b}{a - b - x} = m.$$

Therefore, the concentration of b , at any time t is given by

$$b = m(a - b - x) = ma - mx - mb$$

or

$$b + mb = ma - mx$$

or

$$b(1 + m) = m(a - x) \quad \text{or} \quad b = \frac{m}{1 + m} (a - x).$$

Thus $\frac{dx}{dt}$ for one sided-reaction is given by

$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k \frac{m}{1 + m} (a - x).$$

but m is a constant.

Hence
$$\frac{dx}{dt} = k_1 (a - x)$$

$$\text{or } k_1 = \frac{x}{t} \log \frac{a}{a - x}$$

or the whole change is represented by unimolecular equation. Our results confirm the above mechanism of the reaction.

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